
Ethnobotanical Study of Wound-Healing Plants in Mahur Taluka, Nanded District, Maharashtra

Muneshwar A. S.¹ Parteti L. B.² & Hiwrale S. V.³

¹Department of Botany, L. R. Bharti Arts, Commerce and S. S. R. Bharti Science College, Arni, Dist. Yavatmal, (M. S.)

²Department of Botany, Dr. Ambedkar College, Nagpur, Dist. Nagpur, (M. S.)

³Vinayak Vidnyan Mahavidyalaya, Nandgaon Khandeshwar, Dist. Amravati (M. S.)

Corresponding Author – Muneshwar A. S

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15259689

Abstract:

Medicinal herbs are being used for treating different ailments in different parts of world by different communities. The present study explorations conducted in forest areas of Mahur talukas resulted in the information on the plants used in treating many diseases. This paper deals with wound healing plants. At the time of sports computation minor injuries are occur in tribale areas the indigenous people are use herbal remedies. For which about 10 plants species belonging to 10 Angiospermic families are used.

Key words: Wound healing plants, Indigenous people, Mahur.

Introduction:

Mahur taluka is located in northern part of Nanded district. It is bounded North by Yavatamal district, South by Kinwat taluka of Nanded district East part by Adilabad district of Telangana and West by Pusad taluka of Yavatmal district of Vidarb region. Geographically the Mahur taluka is situated between 19^o49` to 19^o83` North latitude and 77^o 91` to 77^o55` East longitude. The total geographical area of taluka is 52,160 hectares of which 14397.39 hectares area covered with forest and 37762.61 hectares are non-forested area and its population is 86782 (Census-2001), out of this 15.5 percent is inhabited by tribal population of aborigines like Andh, Kolam, Gond, Naikede and Pradhan. Mahur taluka is a thick forested area of Nanded District. The main river is Penganga which flows from the South to North direction.

Materials and methods:

For documentation of medicinal properties information and collection of plant material, several tours were undertaken during the period from 2021 to 2022. Data presented here is based on personal observations and interviews with traditional healers and the methodology used is based on the methods available in the literature. information about medicinal plants was documented in data sheets. For collection of plant material, local informer accompanied to authors. Plant identification was done by using regional floras and flora of adjoining districts. Plants used were compared with major published literature.

Enumeration:

The present botanical explorations conducted in forest areas of Mahur taluka of Nanded District. resulted in the traditional plant uses of 10 plants species belonging to 10 families.

Following data includes botanical name of species, vernacular name, family,

plant part used, method of preparation of medicine.

Sr. No.	Plant Name, Family & Local name	Part Used	Mode of Preparation
1.	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A. Juss. (MELIACEAE) 'Kadu- Neem'	Root	Crush and apply externally till cure.
2.	<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lamk.) Taub. (FABACEAE) 'Palas'	Gum	Apply externally on wounds.
3.	<i>Datura metal</i> L. (SOLANACEAE) 'Kala Dhotra'	Leaves	Crush and apply externally
4.	<i>Dioscorea bulbifera</i> L. (DIOSCOREACEAE) 'Jatashankar'	Root tuber	Crush and apply externally.
5.	<i>Heliotropium indicum</i> L. (BORAGINACEAE) 'Burandi'	Leaves	Past apply externally till cure.
6.	<i>Holoptelea integrifolia</i> (Roxb.) Planch. (ULMACEAE) 'Basmia'	Root	Past apply externally twice only.
7.	<i>Jatropha curcas</i> L. (EUPHORBIACEAE) 'Jungli erand'	Latex	Apply externally till cure.
8.	<i>Parkinsonia aculata</i> L. (CAESALPINIACEAE) 'Bangali babul'	Leaves	Past apply externally till cure.
9.	<i>Tridax procumbens</i> L. (ASTARACEAE) 'Taklani'	Leaves	Crush with 'Jagreen' and past apply externally till cure.
10.	<i>Verbascum chinense</i> (L.) Santapu (SCROPHULARIACEAE) 'Pivla kutke'	Leaves	Past apply externally till cure.

Results and discussions:

Information gathered from Mahur Taluka, Nanded district indicates that the village people of this region possess good knowledge of herbal drugs.

Majority of preparation are from leaves (05), underground parts (03) etc.

To test the scientific validity of the herbal preparations or drugs, clinical studies are required, which can establish therapeutic properties of these preparations for safe use.

References:

- Asolkar, L. V., Kakkar, K. K. and Chakra, O. J. 1992. *Second supplement to glossary of Indian Medicinal plants with Active principles*. Part I (A-K), (1965-81). Publications & Information Directorate, CSIR, New Delhi.
- Chopra, R. N., Nayar. S. L and Chopra, I. C. 1956. *Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants*, Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi.

3. Chopra, R. N., Chopra, I. C., and Verma, B. S. 1969. Supplement to the *Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants*, Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi.
4. Cooke, T. 1958. The Flora of the Presidency of Bombay, Vols 1-3 Reprinted edition, Government of India.
5. Jain, S. K. (ed.)1989. *Methods and approaches in Ethnobotany*, (Society of Ethnobotanists, Luknow),
6. Jain, S. K. and Mudgal, V. A. 1999. *A Handbook of Ethnobotany*, Bhisensingh Mahendrapal Singh, Dehradun.
7. Kapur, L. D. 2001. Handbook of Ayurvedic Medicinal Plants. (CRC Press, London).
8. Kirtikar, K. R. and Basu, B. D. 1933. *Indian Medicinal Plants*, Vol. 1 -4 Publisher L M Basu, Allahabad.
9. Pradhan, S. G., Sharma, B. D and Singh, N. P. 2005. *Flora of Sanjay Gandhi National Park. Borivali-Mumbai*, Botanical Survey of India, Kolkata.
10. Vijigiri Dinesh & Sharma P. P. (2010). Herbal formulations used in treatment of Jaundice by indigenous folklore of Nizamabad District, AP., *Annals of Forestry.*, 18(2): 263-269.